

EDEN ISS

D 7.11 – Animation Works

prepared for

WP 7.1 - Public Engagement

Version: 1.0

Published: 2015-07-31

Approved by:	Barbara Imhof	LSG	Work Package Leader
Approved by:	Matthew Bamsey	DLR	Systems Engineer
Approved by:	Daniel Schubert	DLR	Project Manager

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
2	LSG	R. Waclavicek, B. Imhof, M. Hogle
1	DLR	P. Zabel, M. Bamsey, D. Schubert

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1.0	17.07.2017	René Waclavicek	New document

Executive summary

The Animation Works (D7.11) is part of WP7.1 Public Engagement of the EDEN ISS project. A computer generated movie of three minutes length shall serve as a compressed general description of the project setup during its experimental phase, and the functionality of the Mobile Test Facility (MTF) in particular.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents	4
Acronyms	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS animation works	6
1.2 Purpose and scope of this document	6
2 Animation Sequence	7
3 Summary	11

1 Introduction

1.1 Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS animation works

Animated PC renderings of the greenhouse module for inclusion in various media formats (e.g. TV documentaries)

1.2 Purpose and scope of this document

A chronological video still sequence shows an overview of the animation content.

2 Animation Sequence

Figure 2-1: Location of Neumayer III Station in Antarctic

Figure 2-2: Location of MTF in relation to Neumayer III

Figure 2-3: MTF exterior

Figure 2-4: Service Section interior fly through

Figure 2-5: FEG fly through

Figure 2-6: Feature of different FEG subsystem components (e.g. Atmosphere Management)

Figure 2-7: Abstraction of Global Data Transfer

Figure 2-8: Credits

3 Summary

After first screenings during the last consortium meeting, several amendments will be made.

The part with the different subsystem features will be slowed and enriched with information detail texts.

The global data transfer abstraction at the end of the animation needs to be corrected, since data is sent from Neumayer III Station to Bremen first, and distributed from there.

A preliminary version with reduced size and quality is enclosed. The final animation movie will be finished by the end of August 2017.